

New Records of Yponomeutoid Moths from Azerbaijan (Lepidoptera, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae)

I. G. Pljushtch

Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Bogdan Chmielnicki St., 15
01601 Kiev, Ukraine

makhnark@svitonline.com

Z. S. Gershenson

Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Bogdan Chmielnicki St., 15
01601 Kiev, Ukraine

zs39@mail.ru

Pljushtch I. G. & Gershenson Z. S. New Records of Yponomeutoid Moths from Azerbaijan (Lepidoptera, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae).

Summary. *Yponomeuta rorrellus* (Hübner, 1896) and *Ypsolopha sequella* (Clerck, 1759) are recorded from Azerbaijan for the first time. External characters which useful for identification of the both species are discussed.

Key words: Microlepidoptera, moths, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae, Azerbaijan.

Плющ І. Г. и Гершензон З. С. Новые находки ипономеутоидных молей из Азербайджана (Lepidoptera, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae). Резюме. Впервые для Азербайджана приводятся *Yponomeuta rorrellus* (Hübner, 1896) и *Ypsolopha sequella* (Clerck, 1759). Обсуждаются внешние признаки имаго, необходимые для идентификации этих видов.

Ключевые слова: Microlepidoptera, моли, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae, Азербайджан.

Плющ І. Г. та Гершензон З. С. Нові знахідки іпономеутоїдних молей з Азербайджану (Lepidoptera, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae).

Резюме. Вперше з Азербайджану наведено *Yponomeuta rorrellus* (Hübner, 1896) і *Ypsolopha sequella* (Clerck, 1759). Обговорено зовнішні ознаки имаго, які необхідні для ідентифікації цих видів.

Key words: Microlepidoptera, моли, Yponomeutidae, Plutellidae, Азербайджан.

Introduction

Yponomeutoid moths represent a world wide distributed phytophagous Microlepidopteran families trophically connected with 23 plant families (Gershenson & Ulenberg, 1998). Adults are mostly rather small (wing-span varies from 9 mm to 31 mm). The moths are active at dusk and during the night, whereas during the day-time they are hiding in shady places, particularly under leaves of trees and bushes, so it is rather difficult to catch them. It is possible to attract them by UV light-traps, however yponomeutoids when disturbed often quickly hide among plants and dense grasses near the light source. Their hidden mode of life might be a reason why the diversity of these microlepidopteran species has been insufficiently studies till now. The present paper has aimed to fill this gap and focused on the two species of yponomeutoid moths which are recorded from Azerbaijan for the first time.

Material and Methods

This work is based on the original material collected by the first author in Azerbaijan. Moths were collected at UV light trap in Kalvaz District near Iranian border (38°37'N, 48°21'E) at an elevation of 1,500 m a.s.l.

The collected material is deposited in the Department of the General and Applied Entomology at I. I. Schmalhausen Institute of Zoology of the National Academy of Sciences in Kiev, Ukraine.

Concepts of families mentioned in the paper follow Heppner (1998).

Family Yponomeutidae

Yponomeuta rorrellus (Hübner, 1896)

Material: Azerbaijan, Kalvaz District, Talysh, on light, altitude: 1,500 m asl., 17.07.2003, 2♂, 1♀. (I. Pljushtch)

Figs. 1–2. Forewing pattern.

1. *Yponomeuta rorrellus* (Hübner) 2. *Ypsolopha sequella* (Clerck)

General external characters of imago. Wingspan 16–25 mm (♂ and ♀). Head white. Head structure and wing venation as described for the genus (Friese, 1960; Moriuti, 1977; Gershenson, 1990). Head, palpi, antennae and thorax white. Thorax with five black dots, and one on each tegula. Forewing (Fig. 1) white, suffused with ash-grey and with 25–30 black dots arranged in the three irregular rows, wing apex grey. Hindwing with cilia grey throughout.

Distribution. Europe, W part of the North Caucasus Region (Gershenson & Ulenberg, 1998). Recorded from Azerbaijan for the first time.

Remarks. Externally similar to *Yponomeuta padellus* (Linnaeus, 1758) differing in the features given in the following key.

Key to separate *Yponomeuta rorrellus* and *Y. padellus*

1. Each tegula with one black dot. Forewing white, usually suffused with grey on dorsal area (Fig. 1). Larvae pupate without cocoons in the dense web. Food-plants: different species of willows (*Salix* Linnaeus)*Y. rorrellus* (Hübner)
- Each tegula with two black dots. Forewing white, sometimes suffused with grey along the anterior margin of the wing. Larvae pupate in cocoons. Food-plants: different species of Rosaceae*Y. padellus* (Linnaeus)

Both species do not differ in the structure of the male and female genitalia.

Family Plutellidae

Ypsolopha sequella (Clerck, 1959) (Fig. 2)

Material: Azerbaijan, Kalvaz District, Talysh, 1,500 m asl., at light, 17.07.2003, 3 ♂ (I. Pljushtch).

General external characters. Imago (♂ and ♀). Wingspan 17–22 mm. Head, thorax and background of forewings white. Terminal segment of labial palpus slightly curved, longer or as long as middle segment. Forewing (Fig. 2) with pattern of dark spots and stripes along anterior and posterior margins.

Distribution. Europe, Asia Minor, Israel. Recorded from Azerbaijan for the first time.

Remarks. This species can be easily recognized by forewing pattern. Food-plants: different species of willows (*Salix* Linnaeus).

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